

Cultural Effects of Individual Versus Society in Aravid Adiga's Select Novels

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Abstract

This paper aims to analyze the cultural effects of individual versus society in Aravid Adiga's select novels. The Last Man in Tower and The White Tiger. These novels examine Indian's sacrifices for the next generation, and sometimes they behave crude and cruel manner towards the people they love. In these novels, through the major characters, the culture differs according to their class. So this paper going to argues how the culture differs between individual and society through Aravid Adiga's novels.

Introduction

Aravid Adiga was born on 23rd October 1974. His first book, *The White Tiger* won the Booker Prize in the year 2008, the year of its publication. As far as his professional experience is concerned, he was the former correspondent of the Times magazine. His articles developed in various financial dailies like *The Sunday Times*, *The Financial Times*, and *The Independent*. This shows that he had enough background in the domain of writing. As his family went to Australia, he had some education there. Following on, he went to New York. His journey worldwide and his interaction with many people enriched his writing skills. It also informed Adiga with the reading habits of the people.

Arvind Adiga won the Booker Prize for the novel *The White Tiger* on 14th October 2008 which was published by HarperCollins. *The White Tiger* described the two parts of India, one was dark, and another was light. The reader has sympathy for Balram, who is not a villain in the real sense. *Last Man in Tower* is a novel by Indian writer Aravid Adiga. It was the second novel by Adiga Published by HarperCollins in India in 2011. It tells the story of a struggle of a discharged school teacher named Yogesh A. Murthy, who is affectionately known as Masterji.

Cultural Effects in Individual Versus Society

Indians sacrifice for the next generation, and sometimes they behave in a crude and cruel manner towards the people they love. Characters tend to make decisions based on their life's conditions as time goes by. As Indians are God-fearing people, image-breaking and iconoclasm are not there in classic Indian literature. For example, nobody is discussing extra-marital relationships proudly. Ashok is the landlord's son. He is a product of the western culture in spite of his roots in Indian culture. He finds it hard to bridge the gap between the two cultures. He has western values implanted in him and struggles to obtain feet in the political set up in India. Ashok considers that he is a misfit in Indian circumstances.

Ashok had been married to ultra-modern Pinky Madam. She was disappointed with her husband's interest in political and commercial activities in India. She was interested in western countries and the modern culture there. Husband and wife struggled incessantly. Pinky Madam was angry with him for his false intentions of visiting back in India. She had a lot of western values. When she moves the country, she helps Balram by giving over some money to him. She was not carrying her husband during crises. Ashok's wife means people who have left their origin in traditional society and are being in a modern one. She determined to carve out a niche for herself by adapting herself to the new mindset.

Balram selected advantage of the bickering within Pinky Madam and Ashok. He set his eyes not only on Ashok's money without more on Pinky's person. Lascivious information that Balram makes of Pinky's breasts and bums reflects on his sexual desire for Pinky. Balram brings Ashok everywhere. Since he was a car driver, Balram recognized the many places and people Ashok visited. He could eavesdrop the business discussion in the car. He could espionage Ashok's illegal actions. He studied Ashok carefully. We come across a pathetic character, Mohammad. Mohammad is a poor, hard-working Muslim who needs a job desperately. The landlord he proposed was known for his antipathy for Muslim. The poor boy took a new name, Ram Persad to hide his Muslim identity.

In the old days, there were thousand castes and destinies in India. These days, there are just two castes: Men with Big small Bellies and Men with Big Bellies. And only two destinies: eat or get eaten up (The White Tiger 179).

Munro begins his life as a starving, half-naked child of a remote village in a hilly area and dies in a related state. Balaram, on the other hand, develops from a cringing employee to a multimillionaire employer. This approach to characterization says a lot about the new Indian novel. Characters in the past books did not change so dramatically. Fate ruled their destiny. Balaram changed his future.

Aravind Adiga's Last Man in Tower". The impulse to become rich performs people act less compassionate and humane in the age of globalization. The Man Booker Prize-winning writer Aravind Adiga's debut novel The White Tiger throws light on the dark India which resides untouched by the rapid economic transformations of the 21st century. His second novel Last Man in Tower discovers the crimes connected with real estate, which is one of the booming industries in the age of globalization. It explores how greed to become rich makes people more self-centered and provokes them to do dirty, unimaginable things to other fellow-beings.

In recent decades, the booming real estate industry, which is one of the extension engines of the national economy becomes out to be the richest and highest agency in reordering social life of the middle class. It would be essential to know the concept of the middle class in the Indian context as the novel centers around the Indian middle class. Pavan K. Varma defines the middle class in the Indian context as,

Anybody who has a home to live in and can provide three meals a day, and has way to primary public transport, schooling, and health care, with some disposable income to buy such basics as

watch or a fan or cycle, has already climbed on to the middle-class bandwagon (The Last Man in Tower 138).

The development of the new middle class involves two parallel processes such as “the politics of exclusion” and “the politics of aspiration.” In countries like India, Nepal, and China, the new middle classes are seen as inspirational as they believe “the privileged lifestyles” and “distinctive images” portrayed by the advertising industry and mass media are attainable. As a result, the aspiring middle classes are victimized by exploitative property developers who make a profit out of such famous dreaming.

Conclusion

In *The White Tiger* and *The Last Man in Tower* expresses the culture differs between individual and society through the major characters of these novels. In *The White Tiger* Ashok is the landlord’s son. He is a outcome of the western culture in spite of his roots in Indian culture. He finds the bridge gap between the two cultures. Because Ashok has been married with ultra-modern pinky, madam. She was disappointed with her husband’s interest in political and commercial activities in India. In *The Last Man in Tower* explores how the greed to become rich makes people more self-centered and provokes them to do dirty. As a result, the desire for wealth drives the middle class and underprivileged to do criminal activities. Finally, this paper finds the culture differs between individual and society. Because society readily accepts the new religion. But an individual unable to adopt the new lifestyle but slowly they try to take a new culture. These things are clearly explained in Aravind Adiga’s novels.

References

1. Adiga, Aravind. *Last Man in Tower*. New Delhi: Harper Collins, 2011.
2. _____. *The White Tiger*. New Delhi: HarperCollins, 2009.
3. Anderson, Benedict R. *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. London: Verso, 1991.
4. Barry, Peter. *Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory*. New Delhi: Viva Books, 2010.
5. Farmer, Victoria. “Mass Media: Images, Mobilization, and Communalism.”
6. *Making India Hindu: Religion, Community, and the Politics of Democracy of India*. Ed. David Ludden. New Delhi: Oxford UP, 2005. 250-269.
7. “Fundamental Rights.” *The Constitution of India*. Secretary to the Government of India.
8. Hall, Lex, and Peter Wilson. “Booker for Loner Aravind Adiga with Liking for Aussie Egalitarianism.” *News. The Australian*, 16 Oct. 2008.